

**IMPROVING THE QUALITY OF EDUCATION THROUGH INNOVATIVE
APPROACHES AND DIGITAL TOOLS**

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Annotation. This article analyzes the role of innovative approaches and digital tools in improving the quality of education in general secondary schools. It examines the possibilities of enhancing students’ knowledge levels through the introduction of modern technologies into the educational process, including interactive lessons, electronic learning materials, and data analysis systems. The article also highlights effective methods for identifying educational quality indicators, as well as monitoring and assessment practices. It emphasizes the practical significance of innovative pedagogical approaches and digital tools in improving the quality of education.

Keywords: Open studios, park schools, fractal education, quality of education, innovative approaches, digital tools, e-learning, school education, pedagogical technologies, telecommunication tools, art, design, theater, music, photo and video, STEM, robotics, experimental laboratory, animation studio, startup.

Introduction. In today's globalization world, special attention is paid to the modernization of mechanisms related to the quality of education for the sustainable development of economic and social spheres. In the leading countries of the world with advanced education systems, there are problems such as conducting large-scale scientific research aimed at introducing effective models of education quality management and increasing the efficiency of the educational process through the principles of general quality management based on international concepts. These models and concepts are of urgent importance in improving the quality of education and its assessment systems, and in establishing quality management in educational institutions.

Today, changes are taking place in the education system due to objective processes in society. These changes are innovative and reflect the humanization, informatization and transparency of education. One of the areas of innovation is the implementation of the idea of open education, which requires a revision of views on the functions, essence, features, elements and relationships of the educational process. Transparency implies a constant connection of the educational process with the information environment, adequate, comprehensive and dynamic orientation of the student's personality to culture, taking into account environmental changes in it. Today, the capabilities of the information environment allow the educational process to go beyond the classroom system, which in turn leads to the introduction of new forms of organizing the educational process. These include distance learning, almost distributed learning, modular organization of the educational process, project activities of schoolchildren, extracurricular activities, development and implementation of individual educational programs for students, teaching in open studios without a tutor, etc.

These are classes using telecommunications, in which subjects and objects of education, having a spatial or temporal distance, participate in the educational process aimed at creating educational products and the corresponding internal growth of subjects of education. “When conducting extracurricular activities, students have the right to choose, independently or in agreement with their parents and teacher, the level of study of a subject at a particular level: basic or accelerated. The teaching load is determined for each group of students at all levels of education, taking into account individual educational areas” [1]

Extracurricular (in open studios) “studies involve changing the organization of the educational process:

- by restructuring the study time;
- more intensive study of the program material (block)” [2].

A distinctive feature of the organization of extracurricular learning is that the schedule is drawn up so that each student, regardless of the class in which he is, can study what he chooses. Lessons are held on a common topic for everyone. Such an educational direction performs the function of individualization, ensures the child's right to choose education and provides pedagogical support to the student. It is carried out by schoolchildren in conjunction with the development of an individual educational program, counseling, advertising by teachers of their special and basic educational courses, and informing parents about the mandatory approval and correction of variable educational programs within a specified time. Analysis of individual curricula compiled by students allows for the formation of educational profiles at the higher stage of education. [3] Arriving at a modern school, the student independently decides in which studios and to what extent he will work. Studio profiles can be traditional and include a physics and mathematics studio, a chemistry and biology studio, a social science and political science studio, a literature and art studio, an information technology studio, and a linguistics studio (Russian and foreign languages). At the same time, it is possible to participate in school parks, for example, studios for driving, cutting and sewing or cooking, sports studios. Schools help to improve the quality of extracurricular education through “Open Studios”. An open studio is a creative and educational space that operates on the principles of voluntariness, “openness and cooperation”, organized according to the interests of students, and is focused on practice. Based on the capabilities and needs of the school in the regions, the following studios can be established: Creative (art, design, theater, music, photo-video); scientific (STEM, robotics, experimental laboratory); social (debate, leadership, volunteering studios); digital (IT, media, blogging, animation studio); professional (crafts, entrepreneurship, startup studio)”[4].

Principles of organization:

- voluntary public participation
- open access (non-selective)
- student-centeredness
- practice-oriented
- school-family-community cooperation
- inclusiveness and equal opportunities.

“Open Studios” in general secondary schools are organized in the following stages:

Stage 1. Diagnostics.

- identification of students’ interests (questionnaire, interview).
- proposals from parents.

Stage 2. Design.

- studio plan and program.
- training format (1–2 times a week).

Stage 3. Implementation.

- teachers-mentors.
- training with the participation of external specialists.

Stage 4. Monitoring and evaluation.

- portfolio
- collection of creative works
- student activity

Stage 5. Expected results

- development of students' talents
- meaningful organization of free time
- increased attractiveness of the school environment
- formation of a socially active and independent-thinking personality
- improvement of the quality of out-of-school education

Open studios, as an innovative form of out-of-school education, have high pedagogical effectiveness in determining the personal development, creative potential and professional direction of students, and have a direct positive impact on the quality of general education.

“School parks” are based on the principle of “transparency”, and in this regard, we can distinguish such parameters of the educational process:

In a traditional school, we use them to assess students and compare them, but in a fractal system this is meaningless. The teacher does not assess the student, the teacher records the results of the student’s work. An alternative to the certificate is a review, which is written by the teacher and given to the student. The review reflects the student’s personal achievements in the studios.

A modern school is a socio-pedagogical system that, as a result of a systematic reorganization, has developed from simple to complex, from old to new, and has new opportunities, independence in choosing methods and means of education and upbringing, a modern structural structure, functional tasks, goals, strategy and tactics, educational policy (see Figure 1).

Figure 1. The "Modern School" model.

One of the main features of a modern school is to ensure, activate, and develop vital activity, which is characteristic of voluntary integrative systems. “In this process, the application of approaches such as a systematic approach, a situational approach, a creative approach, a reflexive approach, a coordinated approach, an ethnic approach, a personal-activity approach, a national-territorial approach, and management by results, an innovative approach to the management of educational institutions and their correct use in accordance with their content and

essence require school principals to have the necessary knowledge, skills and qualifications, and are of great importance in the development and improvement of the activities of the institution, as well as in the organization of management activities on a scientific basis” [5]

These approaches “are the methodological foundations of concepts in the direction of organizing management activities on a scientific basis, and serve as a system that includes technologies embodied on the basis of concepts such as integrity, generality, universality, and differentiation in the study and analysis of the object of management, that is, integrative technologies of research”[6]

Conclusion. In conclusion, it can be said that innovative approaches and digital tools in improving the quality of education It was found that modern pedagogical technologies, electronic learning resources and interactive teaching methods help to effectively manage the educational process in schools, increase the level of knowledge of students and ensure their active participation. The introduction of systems for monitoring and evaluating the educational process using digital tools allows for continuous improvement of the quality of education. At the same time, the adoption and application of innovative approaches by teachers and school management is a key factor in improving the quality of education.

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